

Empirical Validation of Signal Predistortion for Nonlinear Distortion Mitigation in RF Amplifiers

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Abstract—Amplifiers are essential components in EMC testing setups. However, it generates levels of distortions that can significantly impact the electromagnetic emissions and susceptibility characteristics of the device under test (DUT), potentially leading to erroneous conclusions and wrong interpretation of test results. In this paper, it is presented the experimental investigation of a signal predistortion method aimed at reducing the power of harmonics and eliminating intermodulation products. This approach is proposed for conducting EMC immunity testing using multi-tone signals. For the linearization with signal predistortion, it is considered a static nonlinear model with memory to define the inverse model of the RF amplifier. This model is based on the Volterra series, specifically named generalized memory polynomial (GMP).

Keywords—Electromagnetic Compatibility, RF Immunity Test, Nonlinearities, Multi-tone, Memory Polynomial, Predistortion, Amplifier.

I. INTRODUCTION

All electronic devices are susceptible to errors and malfunctions caused by electromagnetic interference (EMI). These devices must undergo thorough testing, taking into account their intended usage environment, to ensure adequate protection against potential interference. As discussed in various research studies [1], [2], [3], [4], the combination of numerous radio frequency (RF) signals with diverse modulation types can generate a complex electromagnetic environment (EME) that may not be entirely evaluated using existing EMC standards. Primarily, the EMC immunity standard [5] typically utilizes a single source of interference, employing generic and straightforward waveforms for EMC testing.

However, this testing approach falls short in ensuring safety against the impacts of EMI and in verifying that the equipment can consistently meet acceptable failure levels throughout its life cycle. Depending solely on increasing immunity levels remains insufficient to guarantee that the equipment under test (EUT) will be free from errors or malfunctions caused by simultaneous interference from multiple frequencies in real-life situations [6]. Recent research in the literature [7][8] illustrates an immunity testing procedure that incorporates multiple disturbances, outlining vulnerabilities and EMC failures using multi-tone signals.

Nonlinearities generated throughout power amplifier (PA) during the testing with multi-tone signals may compromise the performance due to in-the-band leakage of out-of-band undesired signals interfering with the desired signal. Due to amplifier nonlinearities, certain amount of power level generates a strength field over the EUT which cause unreliable results in the immunity testing [9][10]. The existence of harmonics and intermodulation products compromises the identification of the specific frequency components that cause malfunctions in the EUT. The harmonics power is low compared to the power of the fundamental frequency, but it can yield a higher field strength due to the frequency response of the antenna. Therefore, it is very important to avoid harmonics and intermodulation products during the EMC testing.

Amplifiers are linear at the lower input power range, while the linearity becomes worse with the higher input power. One method to improve the linearity is to adjust the operating point of input power to the linear region, but the PA efficiency is reduced. A method applying linearization structures was proposed in a previous work developed by Batista [11]. In this present paper, it is demonstrated through physical experiments the feasibility of applying signal predistortion as a method to mitigate the impact of harmonics and intermodulation products during EMC measurements. It's important to note that existing linearization techniques cannot always be considered a universal solution, as their optimality depends on the specific requirements of a particular application. The structure of this paper is outlined as follows: Section II provides an explanation of the methodology, covering signal predistortion concepts and the physical PA. Section III presents the results of the experiments, and Section IV concludes the work.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Signal Predistortion

This linearizing technique enables the compensation of the nonlinear behaviour of a PA, preventing from the nonlinear effects at the PA output by estimating the PA inverse transfer function. The signal predistortion can be applied through two different approach: direct learning (DL) or indirect learning (IL). In this paper, it is used the indirect learning, which determines the nonlinear transfer functions for a nonlinear system establishing relationships between input and output signals, relying on algebraic methods such as Taylor and Volterra series expansion. These functions can only be derived

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when a system adheres to the property of having a single transfer function assigned to its nonlinear characteristic [12].

The theoretical foundation of signal predistortion as a linearization method is established in the concept of the behavioural model of an amplifier [13] which rely on sampled input and output data. Equation 1 illustrates the generalized memory polynomial (GMP) model, an extension of the memory polynomial model. This extension introduces products between the input signal and envelope terms with different time shifts (leading/lagging), commonly referred to as cross-terms.

$$y_{GMP}(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{K_a-1} \sum_{l=0}^{L_a-1} a_{kl} x(n-l) |x(n-l)|^k + \sum_{k=1}^{K_b} \sum_{l=0}^{L_b-1} \sum_{m=1}^{M_b} b_{klm} x(n-l) |x(n-l-m)|^k + \sum_{k=1}^{K_c} \sum_{l=0}^{L_c-1} \sum_{m=1}^{M_c} c_{klm} x(n-l) |x(n-l+m)|^k \quad (1)$$

where $K_a L_a$ are the number of coefficients for aligned signal envelope, $K_b L_b M_b$ are the number of coefficients for signal and lagging envelope, and $K_c L_c M_c$ are the number of coefficients for signal and leading envelope.

The linearization method, with signal predistortion with indirect learning, is depicted in Figure 1. In the forward path, the inverse function of the amplifier, represented in the 'PRE DISTORTION' block placed before the amplifier, is an exact replica of the 'POST DISTORTION' block. In simpler terms, the identification of an inverse amplifier model primarily involves using the output of the amplifier to predict its input. This process, known as postdistortion, is applied after the amplifier. Subsequently, the estimated parameters of the inverse model are copied to create an identical model used for predistorting the input signal before the amplifier [14].

Fig. 1. Predistortion technique scheme. In the forward path it is defined the function to predistorting the input signal and in the feedback or observation path, the parameters characterizing the nonlinear predistortion function in the forward path are estimated and updated.

In the feedback path, the block labelled 'Coefficient Estimator' is for estimating the coefficients of the postdistortion inverse. The coefficients a_{kl}, b_{klm}, c_{klm} from Equation 1 are collected into one vector w of length J , where J is the total number of coefficients. Each component of the vector w is related to a signal whose time samples are over

some period ($n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$). Therefore, all vectors are built into a matrix $N \times J$, which defines the model output as described in Equation 2.

$$\hat{y} = Xw \quad (2)$$

The inverse model estimation for the predistortion, where the input signal is estimated from the output samples, has similar analysis by replacing X with Y as described in Equation 3.

$$\hat{x} = Yw \quad (3)$$

The estimation process is achieved by minimizing the error between the scaled PA output and the input signal $u(n)$, as described in Equation (4).

$$e[n] = x[n] - \hat{x}[n] \quad (4)$$

where $x[n]$ is the input signal and $\hat{x}[n]$ the output signal. In vector notation, e can be defined as $e = x - \hat{x}$ providing a clearer understanding of how estimation algorithms derive the optimal solution for the inverse function. The coefficient estimation, also called learning stage, relies on stochastic gradient algorithms, such as least-mean-squares (LMS) and recursive-least-square (RLS). The objective is to obtain a least-square solution that minimizes the sum of squared errors [14][15].

$$\min_{\hat{w}} = \|e\|^2 \quad (5)$$

Therefore, the coefficients' estimation of the inverse model are defined as the square of the difference between x and Yw , according to Equation (6).

$$w = (Y^H Y)^{-1} Y^H x \quad (6)$$

where w is the coefficient vector of length J , as defined previously. This vector contains the coefficients a_{kl}, b_{klm} and c_{klm} from the Equation 1. Each component of w is associated with a signal whose time samples over some period, and N are collected into a vector.

In summary, the signal predistortion applying indirect learning architecture to find the inverse function $F(u(k))$ to predistort the input signal $u(k)$, could be represented as follows

$$y(k) = G \times F(u(k)) = G \times u(k) \quad (7)$$

where $k = k \times \Delta t$ is the discrete time, $y(k)$ is the amplifier output, $u(k)$ is the input of the amplifier, F is the inverse function of the amplifier and G represents the gain (output/input ratio) of the amplifier.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup, which includes a Class A RF amplifier ZFL-500-BNC+, a multi functional instrument Analog Discovery 2, an oscilloscope Tektronix TDS-2014, and a power supply FAC-662B, is depicted in Figure 2. Incorporating an external oscilloscope into the test setup serves the purpose to validate the generated signal issued from the arbitrary signal generator (ASG). The experimental configuration is implemented in such a way to establish the forward and feedback paths, as depicted in Figure 1, where the PA inverse model can be defined through input and output samples, and the estimation of model coefficients is adapted over some iterations.

Fig. 2. Experimental test setup with RF amplifier (PA), arbitrary signal generator (ASG), oscilloscope (OSC) and power supply.

In Figure 3 is depicted a diagram of the setup experiment. Two functionalities of the multi functional instrument are explored in the experiments, as described below:

- One channel that generates the interference signal on its output port WAVEFORM GENERATOR.
- Two channels to measure the generated interference signal in SCOPE 1, and measure the signal after the amplifier in SCOPE 2.

Fig. 3. Experiment setup diagram.

The data acquisition (DAQ) of the input and output signals are performed using MATLAB[®] software environment through the Data Acquisition Toolbox[™] and the Digilent Toolbox[™], enabling the generation and acquisition from the multi functional equipment. With regard to amplifier specifications, it operates within the frequency range of 0.05 MHz - 500 MHz,

exhibiting a gain between 20 dB and 25 dB. The amplitude of the input signal is adjusted to values close to its compression region (PA is not saturated), as this range is where the PA is expected to operate more efficiently. In accordance with the RF amplifier specifications, its input with no damage is 0.195 V, and the output at 1dB compression point is 0.315 V.

Figure 4 illustrates the input and output relationship of the RF amplifier, where the amplifier exhibits linear behaviour until it approaches approximately 23 dBm, for a specific input range.

Fig. 4. Illustration of the relationship between the input and output power (dBm) applying two-tone test signal to the RF amplifier ZFL-500-BNC+. The difference between P_{out} values refers to the memory effects of the PA over different frequencies.

IV. RESULTS

To conduct the experiments, MATLAB Data Acquisition Toolbox[™] is utilized to control signal generation, configuring data acquisition for hardware interaction, generating data within MATLAB, and transferring measured data to DAQ analog and digital output channels. The Digilent devices impose sampling rate constraints, ranging from 8,192 to 300,000 based on channel types (input and output). As illustrated in Figure 3, the experimental setup is designed with the two input channels (scope) and one output channels (ASG) configurations. The acquisition rate is set to its maximum, generating input signals up to 0.2 V.

Moreover, to mitigate noise during the acquisition, a moving average filter is applied to the amplifier input and output signals. This ensures a clearer reading signal, minimizing potential impacts on the modelling of the inverse function. Therefore, it also imposed restriction to the amplitude level of the input signal. Notably, due to the above limitations, the experiments were conducted with amplitudes below the ASG's signal generation capability, specifically within the range of ± 5 V.

In Table 1, are shown the values of THD for the experiments of one tone signal with and without modulation.

A. One Tone

The parameters of the signal predistortion algorithm, such as memory length, polynomial degree, and gain, for experiments considering one tone signal with or without modulation are determined and set as the algorithm identifies

Table 1. Results of measurements of total harmonic distortion with amplified signal before and after signal predistortion.

Interference Signal	THD	
	Before	After
One Tone	-32 dB	-47 dB
Modulated One Tone	-55 dB	-65 dB

the minimum total harmonic distortion (THD). In respect to the gain parameter of the predistortion algorithm, it is an internal numerical factor that refers to the targeted improvement in gain that the predistortion linearization method aims to achieve. It represents the amount by which the overall gain of the system should be adjusted to accomplish the amplifier expected gain. Therefore, the gain parameter of the predistortion algorithm is adjusted to each type of input signal that is considered in the experiments, avoiding exceeding the maximum input level of the ASG.

1) Without modulation

The first experiment with a one-tone test signal involves a pure sine wave of 10 MHz with an amplitude level equal to 0.06 V (0.12 V peak to peak), which is close to the compression region of the RF amplifier. The predistorted signal is estimated with the following parameters: a memory polynomial model with a memory length of 1, polynomial degree of 4, and an expected gain of 6 dB (output of the amplifier with the predistorted input signal). The parameters set for signal predistortion are defined by finding the lowest value of THD.

As a result, the second harmonic power level was decreased from -47 dB to -73 dB, and the third harmonic from -70 dB and -82 dB. Upon comparison between the up left corner graphic (input signal) with the down right corner in Figure 5, it is observed the effectiveness of the signal predistortion in suppressing the power of the second and third harmonics, that are generated after the signal amplification.

2) With modulation

In reference to the EMC immunity standard [5], the following experiment is a modulated one tone signal $f_c = 10$ MHz, $f_m = 1$ kHz, $A_c = 0.05$ V and $A_m = 0.04$ V. The parameters to estimate the inverse model of the amplifier are memory polynomial, memory length of 5, polynomial degree of 7, and gain of 5 dB, are the model parameters.

In the case of the modulated signal, comparing the up left corner graphic (input signal) with the down right corner in Figure 8, it is observed the effectiveness of the signal predistortion in attenuating the second and third harmonics from -55 dB and -64 to -41 dB and -46, respectively. Also, the predistortion removed the frequencies that are very close to the left and right sidebands of the AM signal.

Figure 5 depicts the results of harmonics attenuation from one tone signal without modulation., and Figure 6 shows the results on reducing the harmonics modulation along with other frequencies close to the sidebands of the modulated signal.

Fig. 5. Comparison of PA input signal, PA output signal, predistorted signal and PA output after one tone predistorted signal is sent as input of the amplifier.

Fig. 6. Comparison of PA input signal, PA output signal, predistorted signal and PA output after a modulated one tone predistorted signal is sent as input of the amplifier.

B. Two Tone

Conversely, for the experiments with two-tone with or without modulation, the highest value of the third-order intercept point (TOI) determines the optimal combination of memory length and polynomial degree.

1) Without modulation

In this experiment, is applied to two tones signals of $f_{c1} = 9.5$ MHz plus $f_{c2} = 10$ MHz with amplitude is $A = 0.06$ V for each tone ($A = 0.12$ V in total), which is located close to the compression region of the amplifier. The results of the TOI values are detailed in Table 2. The estimation model is a memory polynomial model, memory length = 6, a polynomial degree = 4 and gain of 9 dB. The power of the IMD is effectively reduced to less than -50 dB, for both intermodulation products. Before predistortion, the power of the third-order intermodulation stands at $2F_1 - F_2 = -37$ dB and $2F_2 - F_1 = -36$ dB. Post predistortion, these values shift to $2F_1 - F_2 = -55$ dB and $2F_2 - F_1 = -53$ dB, respectively.

Figure 7 depicts the results of attenuating intermodulation products from a two-tone signal without modulation. In the

Table 2. Results of measurements of the third-order intercept point with amplified signal before and after signal predistortion.

Interference Signal	TOI	
	Two Tones	Before
Modulated Two Tones	3.93 dB	9.39 dB
	1.16 dB	7.38 dB

Fig. 7. Comparison of PA input signal, PA output signal, predistorted signal and PA output after two tones predistorted signal is sent as input of the amplifier.

same way as previous signals, comparing the up left corner graphic (input signal) with the down right corner in Figure 7, it is observed the advantage of the signal predistortion in eliminating the third order intermodulation products that are very closed to the boundaries of the two fundamental frequencies of testing.

2) With modulation

The amplitude-modulated two-tone signal $f_{c1} = 9$ MHz, $f_{m1} = 10$ kHz, $f_{c2} = 10$ MHz, $f_{m2} = 20$ kHz, $A_c = 0.04$ V and $A_m = 0.034$ V is considered to perform the experiment. Similarly to the previous scenario, the predistorted signal is estimated using a memory polynomial model with a memory length of 3, a polynomial degree of 3, and gain of 9 dB. From the experiments, it is shown a reduction of more than 30 dB in the power of third-order intermodulation products after signal predistortion linearization. Before the predistortion, the power of third-order intermodulation is $2F_1 - F_2 = -38$ dB and $2F_2 - F_1 = -39$ dB. After applying the predistortion, these values are -57 dB and -76 dB, respectively.

Figure 8 depicts the outcome of reducing intermodulation products from two-tone signal with modulation. Upon comparison between the up left corner graphic (input signal) with the down right corner, it is shown the effect of signal predistortion in eliminating the third order intermodulation products near to the boundaries of the frequency band of operation and the sidebands of the modulated signal, reducing the impact of this kind of distortion into the amplified signal.

Fig. 8. Comparison of PA input signal, PA output signal and PA output signal after AM two tones predistorted signal is sent as input signal, showing the increase in TOI value.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, we conducted experiments to validate the predistortion linearization technique applying indirect learning to the physical RF amplifier ZFL-500-BNC+. As discussed, harmonics and IMD are unwanted frequencies or spurious signals that are not present in the input signal that might impact the measurements of immunity levels in an EMC testing. The experiments were designed to confirm the effectiveness of the proposed method, as detailed in the work performed in [11], wherein a multi-tone signal was introduced to the amplifier.

According to simulation outcomes, the application of signal predistortion significantly enhanced the measurement accuracy by eliminating or reducing unwanted harmonics and intermodulation products, establishing the efficacy of the signal predistortion to improving measurement results. The experimental results support the viability of employing signal predistortion in an electromagnetic compatibility immunity test with a multi-tone test signal, affirming that the proposed method effectively mitigates distortions induced by nonlinearities in the amplifier.

Analysing the method itself, noteworthy observations were made concerning the amplitude of the input signal and the indirect learning approach that was applied. It was noted that as the amplitude increased (without reaching saturation), it required more time to estimate the inverse model of the amplifier or demanded a higher-order polynomial. This implies that as the amplitude rises, more nonlinearities are introduced into the amplifier output. Consequently, additional computational efforts become necessary to accurately model these nonlinearities and calculate the corresponding inverse model. In regard to the approach applied during experiments, it offers one specific indirect learning architecture, and may not be the best estimator of the amplifier nonlinearities. Other estimators, for instance, using a direct learning architecture, could be used to achieve better results.

In conclusion, the signal predistortion can be complex and depends on various factors, including the characteristics

of the amplifier, the chosen predistortion technique, and the specific requirements of the application. Mitigating amplifier nonlinearities when using modulated and multi-tone signals, through predistortion methods, could significantly enhance the accuracy, reliability, and compliance of EMC testing with regulatory standards.

The subsequent phases of this research will involve increasing the frequency range of test signals to include higher bandwidths, to encompass a broader range of challenges encountered in EMC conducted and radiated immunity testing. The research will explore the integration of ASG capable of generating higher bandwidth and more complex signals. This includes digitally modulated signals such as quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) and orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM). Additionally, the study will incorporate the testing of transient signals to assess the predistortion method's performance in scenarios involving rapidly changing signal characteristics. In summary, the integration of signal generators and the utilization of neural networks are key elements in advancing the capabilities of predistortion methods for enhanced performance in power amplifier linearization. These developments can significantly contribute to the field of EMC testing.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Q. M. Khan, L. Devaraj, M. Koohestani, A. R. Ruddle, M. Ramdani, and R. Perdriau, "Synergistic effect of multitone emi on the conducted immunity of integrated oscillators," *IEEE Letters on Electromagnetic Compatibility Practice and Applications*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 77–82, 2022.
- [2] M. Naseef, A. Moskofian, P. Hervé, G. Kokovidis, D. Mendoza, and B. Dowd, "Rf coexistence testing on wireless medical patient monitoring device," in *2022 International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility – EMC Europe*, 2022, pp. 598–603.
- [3] G. Barth, "Benefits of multitone emc immunity testing," *International Journal of RF and Microwave Computer-Aided Engineering*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 355–358, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/mmce.20986>
- [4] K. Harima, D. Akita, and T. Nakamura, "Investigation of radiated immunity testing using white gaussian noise and multitone signals," in *2018 Asia-Pacific Microwave Conference (APMC)*, 2018, pp. 782–784.
- [5] I. E. Commission, *Electromagnetic compatibility (emc) - part 4 : Testing and Measurement Techniques - section 3 : radiated, radio-frequency, electromagnetic field immunity test*, Geneva, Switzerland, 2020.
- [6] K. Armstrong, "Why increasing immunity test levels is not sufficient for high-reliability and critical equipment," in *2009 IEEE International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, 2009, pp. 30–35.
- [7] A. Biondi, H. Rogier, D. Vande Ginste, and D. De Zutter, "Multi-tone emc testing strategy for rf-devices," in *2012 IEEE Electrical Design of Advanced Packaging and Systems Symposium (EDAPS)*, 2012, pp. 89–92.
- [8] L. Devaraj, Q. M. Khan, A. R. Ruddle, and A. P. Duffy, "Comparing simulated impact of single frequency and multitone emi for an integrated circuit," in *2021 13th International Workshop on the Electromagnetic Compatibility of Integrated Circuits (EMC Compo)*, 2022, pp. 107–111.
- [9] J. Hallon, M. Bittera, R. Hart'anský, and K. Kováč, "Immunity against electromagnetic field testing of electrical devices using wireless communication," in *2016 26th International Conference Radioelektronika (RADIOELEKTRONIKA)*, 2016, pp. 75–78.
- [10] J. Li, S. Ma, Q. Liu, Z. Gong, H. Tian, and S. Jin, "Analysis of interference caused by intermodulation in multi-tone radiated immunity tests," in *2018 IEEE International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility and 2018 IEEE Asia-Pacific Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC/APEMC)*, 2018, pp. 660–663.
- [11] N. Batista, M. Quílez, and F. Silva, "Reduction of emc power amplifier intermodulation by using digital signal predistortion," in *2023 International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility – EMC Europe*, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [12] O. Rodríguez Villalón and A. Medina-Rios, "Transfer function with nonlinear characteristics definition based on multidimensional laplace transform and its application to forced response power systems," *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 21, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/12/21/4061>
- [13] P. L. Gilbert, R. N. Braithwaite, and G. Montoro, "Beyond the moore-penrose inverse: Strategies for the estimation of digital predistortion linearization parameters," *IEEE Microwave Magazine*, vol. 21, no. 12, pp. 34–46, 2020.
- [14] D. Morgan, Z. Ma, J. Kim, M. Zierdt, and J. Pastalan, "A generalized memory polynomial model for digital predistortion of rf power amplifiers," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 54, no. 10, pp. 3852–3860, 2006.
- [15] W. Gao and Y. Ren, "A rf predistortion approach to in-device coexistence between 2.4 ghz wi-fi and 4g lte signals," in *2020 IEEE 31st Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications*, 2020, pp. 1–6.